

MORPHOLOGY AND THERMAL STABILITY

OF FIBROUS EUTECTIC COMPOSITES*

G. Haour

Battelle - Geneva Research Centre
1227 - Carouge/Geneva, Switzerland

The morphology of the Cd-CuCd₃ eutectic, revealed by selective sublimation of the cadmium matrix, was observed to be rod-like. No change in the morphology was caused by heat treatment except in areas where fibers displayed fluctuations in diameter. Additions of 1 to 3 wt% zinc to the Cd-CuCd₃ eutectic significantly alter the morphology by causing the rods to develop side-branches and stabilizing plates. Such a modification offers the possibility of controlling the microstructure of eutectics.

*Work performed at the University of Toronto, Toronto, Canada

Introduction

A very small number of rod-like (or fibrous) eutectics have been studied, the most prominent being Al-Al₃Ni. In an effort to widen our knowledge of the formation and the control of eutectic microstructures, a study of the Cd-CuCd₃ eutectic was performed.

Experimental Technique

Specimens of eutectic composition (98.8 wt% Cd), prepared from 99.999 wt% purity materials, were directionally solidified, using a vertical furnace. Growth rate R and temperature gradient G in the liquid near the solid-liquid interface were measured during steady-state growth. The range of $\frac{G}{R}$ ratios thus obtained was : 0.02-150°C/cm². For both directional solidification and subsequent tests of thermal stability, the samples were placed in "Pyrex" ampoules sealed under a low pressure of argon.

The microstructure of the samples was revealed by sublimating the volatile cadmium matrix out of the Cd-CuCd₃ eutectic. This technique of selective sublimation is described briefly (1) and in more detail (2) elsewhere. The CuCd₃ phase is exposed by this technique to a typical depth of 200 microns into the specimen and can thus be observed to advantage by scanning electron microscopy.

Morphology of the Cd-CuCd₃ Eutectic

The CuCd₃ phase is rod-like for growth rates up to 150 cm/hr (Fig. 1). Such morphology is expected in a phase of low volume fraction (7.5%). Similar to that of Al-Al₃Ni (8%). The fibers of CuCd₃ are cylindrical, with diameters ranging from 0.1 to 1.5 micron, depending upon the growth rate. Rods present many defects such as fluctuations in diameter (Fig. 2) in samples grown with low values of G and R .

Thermal Stability

No alteration in the Cd-CuCd₃ microstructure was observed after heat-treatment up to 70 hours at 10°C below the eutectic temperature, except in areas of irregular fibers (shown in Fig. 2), where variations in curvature of the Cd-CuCd₃ solid-solid interface provide a driving force for fast surface diffusion. This results in fibers "pinching off" within five hours of heat treatment at 20°C below the eutectic temperature (Fig. 3).

Modification of the Eutectic Morphology

The main purpose of this study was to investigate the possibility of modifying the eutectic rod-like microstructures. Additions of zinc in the order of 1 to 3 wt% drastically affect the eutectic morphology of the Cd-CuCd₃ system. As zinc is added rods branch out and plates develop (Fig. 4). For additions of 3wt% Zn, the micro-morphology is predominantly plate-like (Fig. 5).

X-ray analysis indicates that, in samples containing 1 wt% zinc, the distribution of zinc is the following : the CuCd₃ phase contains 4 to 5 wt% zinc, whereas no more than 0.1 wt% Zn is found in the cadmium matrix. A detailed explanation of the mechanism for such a modification will be presented in a subsequent article. Briefly, it is believed that this change in microstructure is caused by the very uneven distribution of zinc among the two solid phases, Cd and CuCd₃. Additions of Pb, for example, to the eutectic result solely in the formation of colonies : Pb is rejected equally strongly by both solid phases into a boundary layer ahead of the liquid-solid interface. The characteristic distance of this long-range diffusion field is $\sqrt{D} L$ (diffusion coefficient in liquid over growth rate). Zinc, on the other hand, is incorporated preferentially into the CuCd₃ phase. Additions of zinc result in both colonies and in a short-range lateral composition-gradient in zinc at the interface over a characteristic distance of the order of the inter-rod spacing. The accumulation of zinc ahead of the Cd-phase causes the interface to break down. The CuCd₃ rods lead the Cd-phase. They are in contact with the constitutionally undercooled zinc rich liquid ahead of the Cd-phase. The branching of the rods is a response to this undercooling.

As indicated by the presence of faceted rods and plates, the incorporation of zinc into CuCd₃ significantly lowers the interphase interfacial free energy. This is further shown by the presence of very thin plates of CuCd₃, transparent to electrons (Fig. 6), which are not found in samples without zinc added. These thin plates, less than 0.1 micron thick, represent a surprisingly large interfacial area. To this date, it is believed that no such feature has been reported for an intermetallic phase. In the course of the present work a similar modification from rods to plates has been observed in the Mg-Mg₂Si eutectic.

Conclusion

Revealed by the new technique of selective sublimation, the rod-like morphology of the Cd-CuCd₃ eutectic has been shown to undergo significant changes upon small additions of zinc. This modification should bring more flexibility to the control of eutectic microstructure.

References

1. G. Haour and J.W. Rutter, Met. Trans. 5, 515 (1974).
2. G. Haour and J.W. Rutter, to be published in "Practical Metallography".

Fig. 1 Rods of CuCd_3 phase revealed by sublimation of the cadmium matrix. 2,300 x

Fig. 2 Irregular fibers of CuCd_3 . $G = 20^\circ\text{C}/\text{cm}$. $R = 2\text{cm}/\text{hr}$. 14,000 x

Fig. 3 "Pinched off" fibers after heat-treatment. 6,000 x

Fig. 4 CuCd_3 phase modified by addition of 0.8 wt% zinc. 2,000 x

Fig. 5 CuCd₃ phase modified by addition of 3 wt% zinc. 2,800 x

Fig. 6 Electron transmission micrograph of a thin plate of CuCd₃.